

OCCUPATIONAL DISEASES, THEIR CAUSES AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6945121>

Abstract. *This article describes the modern general theoretical aspects of occupational pathology, and also covers the general principles of classification, treatment and prevention of occupational diseases. In addition, the article contains information on the issues of medical deontology related to occupational diseases, the main occupational diseases that are common in the Republic of Uzbekistan and their characteristics.*

Keywords: *occupational disease, prevention, chemical factors, biological factors, laser rays, scoliosis, caisson.*

ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ, ИХ ПРИЧИНЫ И МЕРЫ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье описаны современные общетеоретические аспекты профессиональной патологии, а также освещены общие принципы классификации, лечения и профилактики профессиональных заболеваний. Кроме того, в статье содержится информация по вопросам медицинской деонтологии, связанным с профессиональными заболеваниями, основным профессиональным заболеваниям, распространенным в Республике Узбекистан и их характеристике.*

Ключевые слова: *профессиональное заболевание, профилактика, химические факторы, биологические факторы, лазерные лучи, сколиоз, кессон.*

INTRODUCTION

Occupational harmful factors in the production process with its technology and equipment (chemical toxic substances, production dust, radiation sources, noise and vibration, low and high atmospheric pressure, low and high temperature, infrared, ultrasound, electromagnetic, laser radiation, etc.) and also the labor process, with the severity and duration of its organization (nervous system, organ of vision, organ of hearing, tension of the vocal chords, actions that are often performed in the same way, in a certain group muscle tension, forced position of the body, etc.) depends.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Occupational disease is a scientifically proven disease that develops due to an occupational harmful factor, is included in the list of occupational diseases, that is, it can develop in production conditions. According to the research of N.F. Izmerov, there are various chemical, physical, biological, genetic, ecological, climatic (nutrition, drinking water supply, life and rest conditions, stress and other conditions) and other factors can cause it.

RESULTS

The use of new chemicals in industry and agriculture requires the study of new preventive measures of new occupational harmful factors. It is possible to prevent the occurrence of diseases as a result of protecting the influence of harmful factors with the help of sanitary and hygienic measures. Technological progress, mechanization and automation of production processes, modernization of equipment, can eliminate harmful factors or reduce them to a safe level. It is necessary to fully study the effects that can be felt by a person during the production

of preventive measures, taking into account social and environmental factors. In addition to the occupational factors causing the development of occupational diseases, the cardiovascular and nervous system, respiratory organs and gastrointestinal tract, hematopoietic organs, musculoskeletal system, which are not etiologically related to labor activity, affects the course of skin and other diseases. Unlike other clinical sciences, occupational pathology is of social importance, because if changes in the worker's health are detected under the influence of harmful occupational factors, it is necessary to allocate material compensation for the damage to his health. The listed main criteria of occupational pathology show that it is one of the complex areas of clinical medicine and requires the development and use of specific methods to objectively diagnose occupational diseases.

Occupational diseases are divided into 2 groups: Group 1 includes only occupational diseases. Factors that cause diseases play a key role in this. These diseases develop only in production conditions and are expressed by specific clinical signs. These include cases of chronic poisoning caused by vibration complications, silicosis, benzene and lead. Group 2 includes non-specific occupational diseases. Common diseases that arise in production conditions with a certain harmful factor are among them. Bronchial asthma, tuberculosis, emphysema, etc. also belong to this group.

DISCUSSION

When determining occupational diseases, it is necessary to follow the following legal provisions:

1. It is necessary to fully analyze the patient's profession and to determine the extent to which harmful factors affect the worker in the course of work, the duration of their exposure, as well as previously experienced general or occupational diseases.

2. It is necessary to get acquainted with the sanitary-hygienic description of the patient's work and working conditions. 3. Information received from the patient must be confirmed by official documents.

4. Taking into account the non-specific clinical signs observed in masker occupational disease, but also found in general diseases (for example, specific anemia symptoms for diseases caused by the impact of lead and organic substances, etc.).

5. Determination of specific reactivity of the body to certain chemicals through the skin.

6. Studying the dynamic development of the pathological process, i.e. abnormal disappearance after the cessation of the influence of the harmful factor, etc.

According to the approved list, occupational diseases are divided into 7 groups:

1. Diseases caused by chemical factors: acute and chronic intoxications with different tropic effects.

2. Diseases caused by industrial aerosols: pneumoconiosis, dusty bronchitis, nasopharyngolaryngitis, allergies.

3. Diseases caused by physical factors: caisson disease, acute and chronic heat stroke, noise, vibration disease.

4. Diseases associated with excessive stress and work of individual organs and systems: coordinate neuroses (in milkmen, violinists, linotypists), radiculitis, arthrosis, bursitis.

5. Diseases caused by biological factors: infectious and parasitic diseases.

6. Allergic diseases: conjunctivitis, rhinitis, bronchial asthma, dermatitis, eczema, etc.

7. Newly formed tumors: dangerous tumors caused by working with consiragens of physical and chemical nature.

Among the occupational diseases there are also injuries related to electric current. All body tissues can be damaged by electric current. But the electric current mostly damages the areas between the input and output path of the electric current - "electrical marks". These tissue changes differ from ordinary burns - tissue damage is deeper, purulent processes are less likely to occur, there are no scars in the burn areas, there is no proportionality of visible local changes and symptoms of electrical damage to organs and tissues, pain is significant due to damage to nerve receptors.

In the case of mild electric shock, strong tremors and contractions of the skeletal muscles, headache, dizziness, chest pain, general weakness, and hallucinations are observed. In severe cases, fainting occurs in addition to the above symptoms. At the same time, there is strong excitement, retrograde amnesia, impaired sensitivity, vision, hearing, smell, the appearance of various pathological reflexes, and an increase in intracranial pressure. The pulse slows down, the heart sounds are weak, and there is a fluttering arrhythmia.

Cardiac arrest occurs as a result of direct impact of electric current on a stray nerve and its center, as well as as a result of cessation of breathing and lack of oxygenation. As a result of the direct impact of the electric current on the respiratory center and respiratory muscles, suffocation occurs and breathing stops.

In order to improve the heart and respiratory function, amyl nitrate, nashatir spir-ti are smelled, caffeine, cordiamine, ephedrine are administered. An aseptic bandage is placed on the burned areas (electric shock marks). He is carefully sent to the hospital in a lying position, accompanied by an observer, because heart and respiratory disorders may recur. Hospital care focuses on improving heart and respiratory function. It is carried out by the method of artificial respiration. To eliminate cardiac fibrillation, 1-3 ml of adrenaline or noradrenaline, 5% calcium chloride and 40% glucose are injected into the heart. People who have been electrocuted are observed for a long time even if they have no complaints.

When the patient has a strong excitement, neuroplegic compounds are injected into the muscle (2% solution of aminazine, dimedrol, pipolfen, promedol), muscle relaxants (dtilin, listepon) are slowly injected into the vein, chloral hydrate 3% solution is taken in the amount of 30-40 ml will be done. Later, in order to prevent possible bleeding, a rubber band, surgical instruments, and blood transfusion systems are prepared.

CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the improvement of working conditions, implementation of healthy medical measures, implementation of the principles of a healthy lifestyle, most forms of occupational diseases (silicosis and other pneumoconiosis, acute pesticide poisoning, skin occupational diseases, etc.) are prevented. agreed to receive.

Participation in the development of engineering and technical tools for the prevention of occupational diseases, the development of hygienic regulations, other sanitary legislation, the scientific organization of work, current preventive sanitary control, sanitary education and preventive work among the labor team. (sanitary rules, safety technical rules, use of special clothing, use of personal protective equipment, treatment-prophylactic diet, transition to liquid regime) must be strictly followed.

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